

**Sabih's Algorithm: A New Algorithm for Finding the MST
with a Worst-Case Time Complexity of $O(E + V \log V)$ and a
Best-Case Time Complexity of $\Omega(E)$, Given Sorted Edges**

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Abstract

This paper presents a novel algorithm for finding a minimum spanning tree of a given weighted, undirected graph, with sorted edges. The algorithm uses greedy techniques, it takes a list of sorted edges, based on their weights, as input, and returns a list of edges that make a minimum spanning tree. The algorithm works by grouping vertices and merging the groups until one group is left. This approach helps avoid detecting cycles as no cycle is added, on the cost of merging. The algorithm has an exact time complexity function of $(E + V/2 \log V/2)$, with linear complexity of $\Omega(E)$ in the best case and $O(E + V \log V)$ in the worst case. The algorithm can be a replacement for Kruskal's algorithm with time complexity of $O((E+V) \log V)$, since we are avoiding the function equivalent to find-set, needed for cycle detection, and merge is the replacement of union, costing a total of $V \log V$ for merging in the entire algorithm rather than $E \log V$ for only find-set operations. Unlike Kruskal's algorithm, the proposed algorithm can also avoid merging entirely in some cases, reducing the time complexity to $\Omega(E)$. Prim's algorithm gives us time complexities $O(V^2)$, $O((E + V) \log V)$ and $O(E + V \log V)$ depending on the data structures used. **If the sorted edges are available**, the proposed algorithm can show a better result for dense graphs where the cost of traversal dominates the rest of the cost ($E \approx V^2$, so $V^2 > V \log V$) as it would traverse **at most** edges E (E or less), unlike prim's which travels edges around $2E$ times, ignoring the common $V \log V$ cost. Unlike Prim's algorithm, that cost might not be included for every graph when using the proposed algorithm, giving it an advantage.

1. Introduction

Minimum Spanning Tree problem, or MST problem, is a crucial part of graph theory and is used in many applications like networking, data clustering, GPS navigation etc. There are traditional algorithms for solving this problem, having their own pros and cons, but they still could use improvement, as they need to perform a lot of basic operations to solve it. These algorithms include Kruskal's algorithm, Prim's algorithm, Boruvka's algorithm etc. This paper introduces a new algorithm that solves the same problem, but with a smaller time complexity function, given sorted edges.

2. Literature Review

MST have extensive applications in bioinformatics, network design, clustering, and the list goes on. Several algorithms have been introduced to find MST in optimal time, for a weighted, undirected graph.

2.1. Classical Algorithms for MST

Kruskal's algorithm is one of the most widely used algorithms for MST problem. This algorithm uses greedy techniques, **takes sorted edges in increasing order as input**, iterates over them and checks if a given edge created a cycle or not; if not, it adds it to the MST, until we get Vertices -1 Edges. The algorithm has the time complexity function of $(E \log V + V \log V)$ in worst case, where V and E are number of vertices and edges, respectively, in a graph. Another famous algorithm is Prim's algorithm, which starts from one vertex and incrementally adds vertices, by finding the lowest cost edge that would connect the given vertices with new one. Its time complexity function can vary based on the data structures used, for example it has the time complexity functions of $(E + V) \log V$, (V^2) and $(2E + V \log V)$, depending on the data structures used. V and E are number of vertices and edges, respectively, in a graph.

2.2 Contribution of the Proposed algorithm

The proposed algorithm uses greedy approaches, **takes sorted edges**, and creates groups and merges them under the conditions mentioned in this paper. No cycles are formed due to this approach, but it does have a cost of $V/2$ for merging the vertices, in the worst case. Since $V/2$ groups are made and are merged $\log V/2$ time in the worst case, it makes the time complexity function $(V/2 \log V/2 + E)$ in the worst case; E since we might iterate over all the Edges, assigning a group is a constant time operation. No merger would happen in the best case, since there would only be one group. Only the Edges would be traversed, giving us time complexity $\Omega(E)$ in best case. E and V represent edges and vertices respectively. The proposed algorithm provides a way that is easier to understand and implement and can be a better replacement for Kruskal's algorithm since it needs less operations. And, better than Prim's algorithm, when edges are presorted and the graph is dense as Prim's algorithm would go over edges about $2E$ times and

the proposed algorithm would do that from $V-1$ up to E time. The increase in the performance would be because the cost of traversing dominates the rest of the cost of the algorithm, as $E \approx V^2 > V \log V$.

3. Proposed Algorithm

The proposed algorithm calculates an MST of a given graph, based on the greedy technique. The algorithm takes input an array of edges, called edges, each containing the two vertices it connects, along with the weight of the edge; and the number vertices, V . The edges in array are sorted based on the weights. The algorithm returns a list containing the edges that form the MST. It uses a double link list, which adds and removes from head and tail in constant time.

Algorithm: Sabih's Algorithm

Input

Input1: Array of edges, with each object containing integer *vertex1* and *vertex2*, integer *weight* of the edge and the array is sorted by *weight*, *edge*

Input2: Number of vertices, *V*

Output: a linked list, contain edges (objects) that make the MST, *mst*

Begin

```
1  groups_lists[V/2]
   // creating an array of linkedlists of size V/2 to store the vertices in each group,
   //as there would be maximum V/2 groups in worst case
2  groups[V] // create an integer array of size V, to store group of each Vertex,
   //initially all indexes are NULL
3  group ← 0 // create an int variable that would store the available group number
4  mst ← new LinkedList //create a linkedlist for the edges for the MST
5  for egde in edges except self-loops//iterate the edges, while ignoring the self-loops
6  | if groups[edge.vertex1] == groups[edge.vertex2] == NULL
   //both vertices don't belong to a group, create a group and add them to it
7  | | create_group( edge.vertex1, edge.vertex2, group, groups_lists, groups )
8  | | group ← group + 1 // group was assigned so increment it by 1
9  | else if groups[edge.vertex1] == NULL
   // if vertex1 doesn't belong to a group but vertex2 does, assign vertex1 to the
   //group of vertex2
10 | | add_vertex_to_group(edge.vertex2, edge.vertex1, groups_lists, groups)
11 | else if groups[edge.vertex2] == NULL
   //if vertex2 doesn't belong to a group but vertex1 does, assign vertex2 to the
   //group of vertex1
12 | | add_vertex_to_group( edge.vertex2, edge.vertex1,groups_lists, groups)
13 | else if groups[edge.vertex1] != groups[edge.vertex2]
   // if both vertices are not in the same group, merge the smaller or equal
   //group into the other one
14 | | merge_groups( edge.vertex1, edge.vertex2, groups_lists, groups )
15 | else
   //this means the edge is connecting two vertices of the same group, it means
   //this edge would make a cycle
16 | | continue
   // skip the current iteration to avoid adding the cycle edge to mst
17 | end if
18 | mst.append( edge ) // if the iteration was not skipped, it means it is safe to
   //add to the mst, since it won't create a cycle
19 | If mst.length == V-1 // MST is complete
20 | | return mst
21 | end if
22 end for
```

End

Function: merge_groups(VERTEX1, VERTEX2 , groups_lists, groups)

Input

Input1: Integer vertex, that belongs to a group , vertex1

Input2: Integer vertex, that doesn't belongs to a group, vertex2

Input3: An array of linkedlists, that stores vertices for all the groups, groups_lists

Input4: An integer array, that stores the group of all the vertices, groups

Output: The function merges the groups of the two given vertices, merging the smaller or equal one into the other, and returns nothing

Begin

```
1      smaller, larger // create two variables to store linkedlists
2      group // create a variable to store the group number of the larger group
3      if groups_lists[group[vertex1]].length > groups_lists[group[vertex2]].length
4          larger ← groups_lists[group[vertex1]]
5          smaller ← groups_lists[group[vertex2]]
6          group ← vertex1
7      else
8          larger ← groups_lists[group[vertex2]]
9          smaller ← groups_lists[group[vertex1]]
10         group ← vertex2
11     end if // assign the longer linkedlist to larger, and smaller to smaller
12     for vertex in smaller
13         // for all vertices in smaller, add them to larger and remove from smaller, and give
14         // them the group of larger group
15         larger.add_vertices(vertex)
16         groups[vertex] = group
17         smaller.remove(vertex)
18     end for
```

End

Function: ADD_VERTEX_TO_GROUP(GROUPED_VERTEX, UNGROUPED_VERTEX, GROUPS_LISTS, groups)

Input

Input1: Integer vertex, that belongs to a group , grouped_vertex

Input2: Integer vertex, that doesn't belong to a group, ungrouped_vertex

Input3: An array of linkedlists, that stores vertices for all the groups, groups_lists

Input4: An integer array, that stores the group of all the vertices, groups

Output: The function assigns the group of the grouped_vertex to ungrouped_vertex and adds the ungrouped_vertex to the linkedlist of the vertices of the grouped_vertex's group and returns nothing

Begin

```
1      groups[ungrouped_vertex] = group[grouped_vertex]
2      // assigns the group of grouped_vertex to the ungrouped_vertex
3      groups_lists[group[grouped_vertex]].add_vertices( ungrouped_vertex )
4      // adds the ungrouped_vertices to the linkedlist of the grouped_vertex's group
```

End

Function: create_Group(VERTEX1, VERTEX2, GROUP, GROUPS_LISTS, groups)

Input**Input1:** First integer vertex, vertex1**Input2:** Second vertex, vertex2**Input3:** The new group number that would be assigned to the new group, group**Input4:** An array of linkedlists, that stores vertices for all the groups, groups_lists**Input5:** An integer array, that stores the group of all the vertices, groups**Output:** The function adds vertices and group number to group_lists and groups, respectively, and returns nothing**Begin**

```
1  groups_lists[group] ← new LinkedList
   // create a new linkedlist for the new group, group
2  groups_lists[group].add_vertices( vertex1, vertex2 )
   // add both vertices to the linkedlist
3  groups[vertex1] = groups[vertex2] = group
   // assign to both the vertices, the new group
```

End

3.1. Time Complexity

The linked list operations take constant time, as linked list is double linked list. Insertion and deletion on head and tail happen in constant time. Creating a group takes constant time as all the operations take constant time, same is with adding a vertex to a group, it also takes constant time. Merging two groups iterates over the vertices of the group with lesser vertices, so it would take $V/2$ operations since the smaller group would have less than or equal to $V/2$ nodes; where V is the number of vertices. The for loop would iterate over each edge, E time; where E is the number of edges. **The edges provided as input are sorted based on weights.**

In the best case, only one group would be created, and all the other vertices would be added to it, since both, creating a group and adding a vertex to a group takes constant time. This would make the **exact time complexity function E** , resulting in **$\Omega(E)$** .

In the worst case, let us assume the number of length vertices is V , such that $V=2^n$, where n is a positive integer. Since we are dealing with the worst case, $V/2$ groups would be created, each containing 2 nodes. After one round of merging, we would be left with $V/4$ groups. Since merging two groups causes only one's vertices to be regrouped, so to get $V/4$ groups, we regroup the vertices of the current $V/4$ groups, each containing 2 nodes, so $V/4 * 2$, or $V/2$ vertices were regrouped to get $V/4$ groups. Likewise, the next round would result in $V/8$ new groups, where $V/8$ old groups' vertices were regrouped, totaling in $V/8 * 4$, or $V/2$, as each group had 4 vertices. **So, to reduce the number of groups by half, $V/2$ vertices are regrouped, in the worst case.** And since we are reducing the number of groups by 2 in worst case, starting with

$V/2$ groups, **we would be changing the groups of $V/2$ vertices, $\log V/2$ time, to get a single group**. Resulting in total $V/2 * \log V/2$ regroupings of vertices. These regroupings don't depend on the number of edges, but in certain cases, the for loop with E time complexity can dominate this regrouping, giving us an exact time complexity function of $(E + V/2 * \log V/2)$, and $O(E + V \log V)$.

For Dense Graphs, E is almost the same as V^2 . We know $V/2 * \log V/2 < V^2$, implying $V/2 * \log V/2 < E$, so E becomes the dominating term, resulting in **$O(E)$ time complexity for dense graphs, in worse case.**

4. Working of Algorithm

The algorithm takes a list of edges, sorted by weight of each edge. It works by creating groups, with each group representing the vertices for a sub minimum spanning tree, the vertices are only stored in the group, while the edges for all the groups are stored in a separate list called mst. The edges in the mst list make a complete MST when its length reaches $V-1$. Groups help decide if a edge is safe or not, if it is safe, it is added to the mst. If the edge is trying to join two vertices, then it's not a safe edge as it would make a cycle in a group, that would result in a cycle in a part of the MST. A edge is safe if it does one of the following

- Joining two ungrouped vertices, creating a new group, given it's not a self-loop.
- Joining a grouped and an ungrouped vertices.
- joining two vertices from different groups.

The algorithm iterates over the sorted edges, creating, and merging groups until one group is formed, while adding the safe edges to the MST. When one group is formed, MST is complete.

4.1. Example of The Best Case

Figure 1 : how Sabih's algorithm works on a given graph in the best case scenario

We start with a graph, as shown in the image above, the algorithm traverses over the edges, starting with the one with weight 1, since both the vertices connected to it are not grouped, we group them together under group 1, and label the edge as safe, adding it to the MST edges, as we would add all the rest safe edges, as well. The next edge is with weight 2, since one vertex is grouped and the other is not, we add the one without a group to the group of the other one, in this case, group 1, marking the edge as safe. Then the algorithm traverses over the edges with weights 3, 4 and 4, and adds them to group 1, as they are not in a group, but the edge has connected them to a vertex that is in a group. When the next edge with weight 5 is looked at, it connects two vertices with the same group, this edge is marked as unsafe as it would create a cycle in the MST and is not added to the list of edges for MST. Then the next edge is traversed, which joins the last vertex without a group to a group, it is also added to the group 1, and the MST is complete.

4.2. Example of The Worst Case

Figure 2: how Sabih's algorithm works on a given graph in the worst case scenario

The algorithm starts iterating over the edges, string with the one with weight 1, as shown in the figure. Since both vertices don't belong to a group, they are added to a group called group 1. The same happens for edges with weights 1, 2 and 2; the vertices they connect don't belong to a group, so they are added to group 2, group 3 and group 4 respectively, in the next three iterations. All the edges are safe so far and added to the MST edges list. The next edge is connecting group 3 and group 4, with a weight of 4, since connecting two different groups doesn't form a cycle, the edge is marked safe, added to the MST edges list, and the two groups are merged into one. In this case, the nodes of group 4 are, one by one, removed from the group 4 and added to group 3. The next edge also joins two groups with weight 5, this edge is also added to the MST edges list,

and group 1 is merged into group 2, since these two were connected by the current edge. In the next two iterations, edges with weights 6 and 7 are traversed, since they both connect the vertices of the same group, they are considered unsafe and hence ignored. The next edge connects group 2 and group 3, group 3 is merged into group 2, creating a single group. The current edge is safe and added to the MST edges list, making the length of the MST edges list $V-1$, where V is the number of vertices. This completes the MST and the algorithm stops.

5. Discussion

The algorithm discussed in this paper is a big improvement, in terms of exact time complexity function and basic operations performed, over the existing Kruskal's algorithm for finding MST. The algorithm has an exact time complexity function of $E + V/2 * \log V$, with time complexity of $\Omega(E)$ in the best case and $O(E + V \log V)$ in the worst case. The algorithm needs the edges to be sorted, just like in Kruskal's algorithm. While the merge function, in the proposed algorithm can be considered equivalent to union operation in Kruskal's algorithm, the proposed algorithm doesn't have any find-set function, that is a crucial part of Kruskal's algorithm for cycle detection. The proposed algorithm can do the same thing just by checking the group of the vertices, in constant time. Since, unlike Kruskal's algorithm, the proposed algorithm doesn't need to check find-set for all the edges it traverses, which costs $\log V$ time for every edge, in the worst case, a lot of operations are reduced. In the worst case the proposed algorithm might need $O(V \log V)$ for merging all the vertices, or group, into a single MST. It can be done in less operation, depending on how many groups are formed, ranging from one to $V/2$ groups, resulting in E to $E + V \log V$ time complexities. In case only one group is formed, like in the best case, there would be no merging operation performed, and the MST would be constructed in linear time, making this algorithm an obviously better choice than Kruskal's algorithm in such cases.

When we have the edges sorted, the proposed algorithm can outperform Prim's algorithm in some cases, like in dense graphs where the traversal cost is bigger than other operations. In dense graphs $E \approx V^2$, making $E > V \log V$. Prim's algorithm traverses the edges $2E$ times, and has the additional cost of about $V \log V$, compared to that the proposed algorithm traverses the edges **at most** E times, and might perform about zero to $V \log V$ operations for merging.

6. Conclusion

This paper introduces a novel algorithm for finding MST of a graph, by grouping vertices and avoiding cycle detection, unlike traditional algorithm like Kruskal's algorithm. Considering both algorithms are getting sorted edges as input, the proposed algorithm has better time complexity of $\Omega(E)$ in the best case and $O(E + V \log V)$ in the worst case, compared to Kruskal's algorithm and can be used as a better substitute. This algorithm can also be substituted for Prim's algorithm in for dense graphs for better results when the edges are sorted. In conclusion the proposed algorithm is one step forth in making and using better and more efficient algorithms for finding the MST of a given undirected graph.

7. References

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